

IMPLEMENTATION OF REGIONAL INNOVATION POLICIES THROUGH THE ROLE OF REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT PLANNING AGENCY (BAPPEDA) RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT OF PALEMBANG CITY

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Abstract

This research aims to analyze the implementation of regional innovation policy in Agency of Planning and Regional Development, Research and Development (Bappeda Litbang) Palembang City. The problem is paying attention to how Bappeda Litbang Palembang City can implement regional innovation policies in Palembang City. In order to approach this problem, theoretical references from George C. Edward III with four dimensions that affect policy implementation, such as communication, resources, disposition, and bureaucratic structure or bureaucratic system. The data were assembled through literature study, observation, and analyzed qualitatively with a descriptive approach. This study deduced that the four dimensions, such as, the communication dimension, the resource dimension, the disposition dimension, and the bureaucratic structure dimension show positive results. However, there are still obstacles discovered, such as the need to strengthen the socialization and education, strengthen the human resources, commitment of regional apparatus leaders and evaluation of innovation implementation

Keywords: *Implementation, Regional Innovation, Public Policy.*

INTRODUCTION

Regional governments have duties and responsibilities in providing public services to the community. Routine provision of public services is usually given regularly and repeatedly. The development of information and communication technology has increased public expectations, thus providing encouragement for the government to adapt to fast, efficient, and transparent services (Utami, 2023). Therefore, public organizations need to innovate and realize good governance and excellent service to the community (Zulfia & Frinaldi, 2023). This is in line with Law Number 23 of 2014 concerning Regional Government, which emphasizes innovation as an instrument in supporting the effectiveness of performance in the administration of government. The effectiveness of government performance can improve the quality of services to the community in the future, thereby simultaneously creating an increase in public satisfaction (Republic of Indonesia, 2014).

Government Regulation (PP) Number 38 of 2017 concerning Regional Innovation establishes an agency or unit that handles research and development as a fostering element for regional innovation at the local government level. (Republic of Indonesia, 2017). Referring to the government regulation, one of the units in question is the Palembang City Planning and Development, Research and Development Agency (Bappeda Litbang). The Palembang City Research and Development Agency (Bappeda Litbang) as the Supervisor and implementer of regional innovation policies in Palembang City has a legal basis in efforts to support the implementation of Regional Innovation, including Palembang City Regional Regulation Number 4 of 2025 concerning the 2025-2029 RPJMD which places the issue of Innovation as an aspect in regional development, Palembang Mayor Regulation Number 24 of 2023 concerning Regional Innovation and Palembang Mayor Decree Number 492-KPTS / BPP-LITBANG / 2023 of 2023 concerning Regional Innovation within the Palembang City Government. In addition, concrete steps to build a culture of Innovation through the declaration of an Innovation culture and the holding of the Palembang City Innovation Competition (Palembang City Government, 2023). Government Regulation Number 38 of 2017 concerning Regional Innovation explains the implementation of innovation in regions through a series of stages starting from the proposal stage, the innovation determination stage, the trial stage and the innovation implementation

stage (Republic of Indonesia, 2017). The next stage of assessing the implementation of regional innovation and providing appreciation awards and regional incentive funds to regional governments that successfully implement innovation has been regulated in the Assessment and Provision of Awards and/or Incentives for Regional Innovation (Ministry of Home Affairs, 2018). In 2025, Palembang City obtained an index score of 88.02 with a very innovative predicate and received the Innovative Government Award (IGA) from the Minister of Home Affairs in the Regional Innovation Index (IID) Assessment (Ministry of Home Affairs, 2025).

Table 1. Results of the Palembang City Regional Innovation Index Assessment for 2021-2025

Year	Number of Innovations	IID Value	Predicate
2025	355	88.02	Very innovative
2024	355	84.28	Very innovative
2023	260	68.13	Very Innovative
2022	202	55.52	Innovative
2021	107	55.19	Innovative

Source: Data Processed from the Palembang City Research and Development Agency

Based on the table above, the development of the number of innovations in Palembang City experienced an increasing trend in 2021-2025. The accumulated number of innovations obtained in 2025 based on Palembang Mayor Regulation Number 24 of 2023 concerning Regional Innovation and Palembang Mayor Decree Number 492/KPTS/BPP-LITBANG/2023 concerning Regional Innovation within the Palembang City Government was 355 innovations (Palembang City Government, 2023). However, the number of innovations reported to the regional innovation index application system for 2025 is only 200 for the assessment stage. Several innovations are still suboptimal because they do not meet the standards and criteria set by the Palembang City Research and Development Agency (Bappeda Litbang) for inclusion in the assessment stage. Furthermore, the implementation of regional innovations emphasizes that innovations that have been implemented for more than two years require updates during the innovation implementation process. This presents a challenge, as some old innovations cannot be reported back to the regional innovation index application system because they have not been updated or are no longer running.

Several previous literature reviews have discussed the implementation of regional innovation policies. Research by Wahyuni & Aziza (2017) states that strengthening Balitbangda as the regional innovation coordinator is done by emphasizing human resources (HR) and budget allocation (Wahyuni & Aziza, 2017). Another study by Zulfia et al. (2023) states that the implementation of regional innovation policies has been going quite well, but there are still obstacles, namely a lack of seriousness and commitment from leaders (Zulfia et al., 2023). Matriddi et al. (2023) state that stakeholder commitment is essential for generating regional innovation (Matriddi et al., 2023). This study uses the theory of George C. Edward III, hereinafter referred to as G. Edwards III (1980), which states that there are four dimensions that influence policy implementation, namely communication, resources, disposition, and bureaucratic structure or bureaucratic system (George C Edwards, 1980). The choice of theory is based on how the success of implementing regional innovation policies is not only the application of Palembang Mayor Regulation Number 24 of 2023 concerning Regional Innovation but success can also be influenced by the interaction process between the Palembang City Bappeda Litbang and other stakeholders. Based on the background of the problems mentioned, this research article aims to analyze how the implementation of regional innovation policies through the role of the Palembang City Bappeda Litbang and the obstacles faced in its implementation using the George C. Edward III Theory approach.

METHOD

The research was conducted using a qualitative method with a descriptive approach. This research is a descriptive qualitative study. Data collection was conducted through literature review and observation. Then, it was analyzed qualitatively using a descriptive approach. This research focuses on the review of Regional Innovation policy implementation using the four-dimensional approach of George C. Edward III's Theory: communication, resources, disposition, and bureaucratic structure or bureaucratic system.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Communication Dimensions

According to George C. Edward III in Nugroho (2020), communication is a variable that influences policy implementation. The success of implementation is determined by the extent to which a policy can be communicated by policy implementers and the response of the parties involved (Nugroho, 2020). The implementers of regional innovation policies at the Palembang City Bappeda Litbang in communicating with regional apparatus in the Palembang City government environment through socialization activities and technical guidance to provide information and understanding to regional apparatus to implement regional innovation. Socialization, mentoring and coaching are carried out periodically every year by directly inviting regional officials to the Palembang City Bappeda Litbang, as well as conducting direct visits to regional officials to explore new innovations and develop the sustainability of old innovations.

This is because the sustainability of an innovation can be achieved not only through new innovations but also through updating previous innovations within the regional apparatus (Wardani & Apriani, 2023). Therefore, intensive and well-established communication with regional apparatus is necessary. This can facilitate policy implementers' monitoring and supervision of innovation implementation. Given that some regional government agencies still haven't implemented innovation, ongoing coaching and education efforts are needed to address the obligation to innovate and the need for innovation in governance. Furthermore, communication efforts are needed to build commitment among regional government leaders to foster innovation within their organizations.

Resource Dimension

Resources play a crucial role in achieving successful public policy implementation. Implementation cannot proceed effectively without adequate resources. According to George C. Edward III, in Nugroho (2020), the existence of resources, including human resource skills and other supporting resources, is crucial for successful policy implementation (Nugroho, 2020). Human resources at the Palembang City Regional Development Planning Agency (Bappeda Litbang), particularly the Research and Development Division, already possess adequate competencies and a sufficient understanding of the Regional Innovation Policy. Policy implementers are sufficiently capable of providing outreach and assistance to regional officials in implementing and reporting regional innovations. This assistance is provided by completing supporting documents and data according to indicators on the regional innovation index website to ensure that innovations meet quality and maturity standards.

This can be seen from the number of innovations reported to the regional innovation index application system in 2025, which amounted to 200 innovations with an index score of 88.02 and a very innovative predicate (Ministry of Home Affairs, 2025). This achievement increased compared to 2024, which amounted to 145 innovations with an index score of 84.28 and a very innovative predicate (Ministry of Home Affairs, 2024). Although the Palembang City Research and Development Agency has sufficient human resources in terms of competency and understanding of innovation policies, it is still necessary to strengthen human resources in implementing regional innovation and inputting regional innovation indexes at the regional apparatus level. Furthermore, the facilities and infrastructure to support the implementation of innovation policies are already adequate at the Palembang City Research and Development Agency (Bappeda Litbang). However, the use of technology through the ASIK (Research and Development Information System Application) platform still requires development and improvement to support innovation data management and collection, as well as innovation dissemination within the Palembang City Government.

Policy implementation must also be accompanied by adequate budget allocation to ensure effective regional innovation implementation. According to Lestari et al. (2024), inadequate budgetary resources lead to suboptimal implementation (Lestari et al., 2024). Lack of incentives for innovation reporters, inadequate documentation, and supporting infrastructure can also hinder innovation implementation (Sigalingging & Kartika, 2025). Therefore, to improve the quality of innovation implementation, strengthening the organization's internal role in terms of human resource capacity and budget is still necessary (Simanungkalit & Prasajo, 2020).

Disposition Dimension

The disposition or attitude of the implementer is crucial for the implementation of public policy. If the individual implementing the policy has a positive attitude, implementation will align with the wishes of the officials above them. However, if the implementer's attitude is unsupportive, implementation will not be successful. According to George C. Edward III in Nugroho (2020), successful implementation depends not only on the

implementer's ability but also on the willingness and commitment to implement the policy (Nugroho, 2020). The implementers' attitudes toward implementing the Regional Innovation Policy have been positive. Palembang City's Bappeda Litbang staff are committed to implementing the Regional Innovation Policy and understand their duties and responsibilities, as directed by policymakers. Furthermore, the declaration of a culture of innovation demonstrates the commitment of leaders and implementers to implementing the innovation policy.

Dimensions of Organizational Structure (Bureaucratic System).

According to Edward III (in Nugroho, 2020), organizational structure is related to the suitability of the bureaucratic organization responsible for implementing public policy. The challenge is how to avoid a fragmented bureaucracy and thus unimpede the implementation process. Excessively lengthy procedures can make innovation difficult to implement. Manar and Alfirdaus (2023) state that innovation requires easy-to-understand processes and procedures. This provides bureaucratic and administrative support, enabling innovation to proceed and yield results (Manar & Alfirdaus, 2023). The organizational structure for implementing regional innovation policies is well established. The Palembang City Research and Development Agency (Bappeda Litbang) has Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) and legal frameworks can provide certainty and effectiveness in the implementation of regional innovation. The implementation of regional innovation is regulated in Government Regulation Number 38 of 2017 concerning Regional Innovation (Republic of Indonesia, 2017).

The Palembang City Government issued Mayoral Regulation Number 24 of 2023 concerning Regional Innovation. This regulation stipulates that regional apparatuses are required to propose innovations annually to the research and development division of the Palembang City Regional Development Planning Agency (Bappeda Litbang). Furthermore, the Palembang City Regional Development Planning Agency (Bappeda Litbang) carries out the tasks of evaluating, disseminating, fostering, mentoring, and supervising innovations within regional apparatuses (Palembang City Government, 2023). However, the implementation of regional innovations still requires periodic evaluation to ensure compliance with Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) and applicable regulations. This is because some innovations reported to the Palembang City Research and Development Agency (Bappeda Litbang) lack the maturity and completeness of documentation required for reporting to the regional innovation index application system. Therefore, periodic evaluations are necessary for both innovations experiencing challenges and those that are progressing well. This evaluation is conducted to maintain an adaptive bureaucratic structure and improve innovation implementation in the future.

CONCLUSION

A review of the implementation of regional innovation at the Palembang City Regional Development Planning Agency (Bappeda Litbang) has shown positive results across four dimensions: communication, resources, disposition, and organizational structure. However, challenges related to education and commitment from regional officials have been identified in the communication dimension that could potentially lead to future obstacles to implementing regional innovation. In the resource dimension, it was found that there is a need to strengthen resources, especially at the regional apparatus level. Furthermore, in the bureaucratic structure dimension, there are challenges in improving the quality and impact of innovation, necessitating regular evaluation of innovation implementation.

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